

Getting Started with Deep Learning

What is this lecture about?

- Assumes close to zero technical knowledge about deep learning.
- An introduction to deep learning at a high level.
- Steps to get started with deep learning hands-on.
- Pointers to more resources.

What is this lecture NOT about?

- In-depth discussion about how things work "inside the box".
- Technical discussion about implementation.
- Machine Learning.

How is Deep Learning Useful?

 Analytics Insight

OpenAI's GPT-3 Is Powering These Industries With Unique

...

GPT-3, One of OpenAI's most renowned language models, is being used by more than 300 applications for searches, conversations, text ...

3 weeks ago

 The Verge

DeepMind's StarCraft 2 AI is now better than 99.8 percent of all human players

The Google-owned AI lab's more sophisticated software, still called AlphaStar, is now grandmaster level in the real-time strategy game, capable ...

30 Oct 2019

 VentureBeat

Autonomous trucking company Plus will use AI and billions of miles of data to train self-driving semis

The safest self-driving vehicle platforms are those that have ... This is accomplished in large part by training so-called "deep learning" ...

4 weeks ago

 HPCwire

Can Deep Learning Replace Numerical Weather Prediction?

The weather and climate supercomputing community is no stranger to deep learning, but it has hitherto mostly been used to augment NWP ...

3 Mar 2021

Alpha Fold

- An AI that predicts the 3D structure of a protein based solely on its genetic sequence.
- Why? Structure of a protein influences how it behaves in an organism. Malfunction often leads to disease.
- Modelling the physical structure of a protein is difficult. Genetic sequencing is easier.
- How? A deep neural network that predicts the distance between pairs of amino acids, and angles between chemical bonds that connect those amino acids.
- Won first place at CASP13 global competition.

Source: <https://deepmind.com/blog/article/AlphaFold-Using-AI-for-scientific-discovery>

DeepLabCut

- 3D markerless pose estimation using neural networks.
- Able to track various body parts in multiple species across a broad collection of behaviours.
- Available as a Python package that is open source, fast, robust and requires minimal training data to fine tune to your use case.

Source: <http://www.mackenziemathislab.org/deeplabcut>

Brain to text communication

- User imagines writing – neural network predicts user intentions.
- How? Neural activity in the motor cortex is recorded and fed into a Recurrent Neural Network. Network predictions are denoised with a language model.
- User was able to “write” 90 characters per minute at >99% accuracy with a general-purpose autocorrect (Age adjusted able-bodied smartphone typing speeds ~115 cpm).

Source: <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.07.01.183384v1.full.pdf>

What is Deep Learning?

Programming vs Deep Learning

VS

How would you traditionally design code that categorises images of dogs and cats?

VS

Traditional software development

VS

Traditional software development

Deep Learning

VS

Traditional software development

Traditional software development automates the process of executing instructions

Deep Learning

Deep learning automates the process of defining those instructions!

AI vs ML vs DL

What is a Deep Neural Network?

One Neuron

Source: <https://training.seer.cancer.gov/anatomy/nervous/tissue.html>

- Modelled after neurons in the brain.
 - Each neuron takes input from multiple sources.
 - Neuron aggregates information and passes output to next layer.
- Fundamental unit – an artificial neuron, a perceptron.

Many, many neurons

Simple Neural Network

Deep Learning Neural Network

● Input Layer

● Hidden Layer

● Output Layer

Source: <https://thedata scientist.com/what-deep-learning-is-and-isnt/>

How does a Neural Network learn?

- Through a "Trial-and-Error" process – via gradient descent.
- The network's output is compared to a label (the truth).
- The loss (error) is calculated and used to guide the learning process.

Keywords: Gradient Descent, Back-Propagation.

How do I get started with Deep Learning?

Getting started – a checklist

The Basics

- Understand basic Data Science concepts.
- Understand basic Deep Learning concepts.
- Understand the Deep Learning workflow.
- Know how to code (in Python).
- Choose a DL library - TensorFlow or PyTorch.
- Get your hands dirty – run some code, train a model.

The Next Steps

- Prepare the right dataset.
- Pick the right tool - learn about neural network variants.
- Get the right computing hardware.
- Think about deployment.

Essential concepts you need to know

General Data Science

- Data cleaning and wrangling.
- Training vs. Validation vs. Test datasets.
- Overfitting vs. Underfitting a model.
- Common evaluation metrics.
- Supervised vs. Unsupervised learning.
- Regression vs. Classification vs. Clustering.

Deep Learning

- General structure of a neural network – cells and layers.
- How NNs learn – loss function, back-propagation, SGD.
- Key hyperparameters – batch size, number of epochs, learning rate.....
- Handling inputs to the NN – input shape, order of dimensions (e.g. B, H, W, C).
- Handling outputs of the NN – output shape, order of dimensions, Logits, Softmax.

Some deep learning resources

Beginner

- Check with your local university for workshops, events and seminars.
- Youtube: 3Blue1Brown, Two Minute Papers, Brandon Rohrer.
- Blogs and articles: <https://towardsdatascience.com/>
- Online courses: MOOC.org, Coursera...
- <https://playground.tensorflow.org/>
- Galaxy: <https://training.galaxyproject.org/>

Intermediate

- Youtube: Aurélien Géron, Arxiv Insights, Henry AI Labs, Yannic Kilcher.
- Blogs and articles: <https://towardsdatascience.com/>
- Papers: <https://arxiv.org/list/cs.AI/recent>

Galaxy

“Galaxy is a scientific workflow, data integration, and data and analysis persistence and publishing platform that aims to make computational biology accessible to research scientists that do not have computer programming experience.”

<https://training.galaxyproject.org/>

Age prediction using machine learning

Basics of machine learning

Classification in Machine Learning

Clustering in Machine Learning

Deep Learning (Part 1) - Feedforward neural networks (FNN)

Deep Learning (Part 2) - Recurrent neural networks (RNN)

Deep Learning (Part 3) - Convolutional neural networks (CNN)

Interval-Wise Testing for omics data

Introduction to deep learning

Introduction to Machine Learning using R

Machine learning: classification and regression

PAPAA PI3K_OG: PanCancer Aberrant Pathway Activity Analysis

Machine learning Pan-cancer cancer biomarkers

oncogenes and tumor suppressor genes

Regression in Machine Learning

Text-mining with the SimText toolset

Galaxy – research direction and candidate models

Research direction	Data	Data types	Candidate models
Sequence analysis	Sequence data (DNA sequence, RNA sequence, <i>et al.</i>)	1D data	CNN, RNN
Structure prediction and reconstruction	MRI images, Cryo-EM images, fluorescence microscopy images, protein contact map	2D data	CNN, GAN, VAE
Biomolecular property and function prediction	Sequencing data, PSSM, structure properties, microarray gene expression	1D data, 2D data, structured data	DNN, CNN, RNN
Biomedical image processing and diagnosis	CT images, PET images, MRI images	2D data	CNN, GAN
Biomolecule interaction prediction and systems biology	Microarray gene expression, PPI, gene-disease interaction, disease-disease similarity network, disease-variant network	1D data, 2D data, structured data, graph data	CNN, GCN

Figure 10: Different architectures of neural networks for different fields of bioinformatics.

The deep learning workflow

Deep Learning is part-Art part-Science

Priorities:

- Data volume and quality
- Loss function
- Model architecture and size
- Fine tuning

This is an over-simplification of the deep learning workflow as a linear model.
The real world is messy and non-linear.

Coding in Python

- Python is by a significant margin the most popular in language in the DL community.
- Understand that there are multiple versions of Python – may or may not affect you.
- Know about Python packages – if you need it, it probably exists somewhere.
- Commonly used packages for DL – numpy, pandas, matplotlib, opencv, (scipy, scikit-learn).

VS **PYTORCH**

Google Search Trends

TENSORFLOW VS KERAS VS PYTORCH

Data source: Google Trends

Getting started with TensorFlow and PyTorch

- The official websites are a great resource.
- <https://www.tensorflow.org/tutorials>
- <https://pytorch.org/tutorials/>
- You can easily run the tutorial code without installation:

The screenshot shows the top of a PyTorch tutorial page. At the top, there are three buttons: "Run in Google Colab" (circled in yellow), "Download Notebook", and "View on GitHub". Below the buttons, the title "PYTORCH: NN" is displayed. The text describes a third-order polynomial trained to predict $y = \sin(x)$ from $-x$ to π by minimizing squared Euclidean distance. It mentions that the implementation uses the `nn` package from PyTorch. Below the text is a code block with the following Python code:

```
import torch
import math

# Create Tensors to hold input and outputs.
x = torch.linspace(-math.pi, math.pi, 2000)
y = torch.sin(x)
```


The screenshot shows the top of a TensorFlow 2 quickstart tutorial page. At the top, there is a breadcrumb trail: "TensorFlow > Learn > TensorFlow Core > Tutorials" and a star rating of five stars. The title "TensorFlow 2 quickstart for beginners" is displayed. Below the title, there are three buttons: "Run in Google Colab" (circled in yellow), "View source on GitHub", and "Download notebook". The text below the buttons states: "This short introduction uses [Keras](#) to:" followed by a numbered list:

1. Build a neural network that classifies images.
2. Train this neural network.
3. And, finally, evaluate the accuracy of the model.

Below the list, it says: "This is a [Google Colaboratory](#) notebook file. Python programs are run directly in the browser—a great way to learn and use TensorFlow. To follow this tutorial, run the notebook in Google Colab by clicking the button at the top of this page." followed by another numbered list:

1. In Colab, connect to a Python runtime: At the top-right of the menu bar, select *CONNECT*.
2. Run all the notebook code cells: Select *Runtime > Run all*.

Now the fun begins....

Training your own, real model.

Your dataset

- Good quality data is essential – garbage in, garbage out.
- Think about:
 - What types of data you will need.
 - How much data you will need.
 - The quality of the data – balanced, low noise, representative.
 - How you will collect data.
 - How you will store data in a manner that makes retrieval efficient.
 - How you will label your data.

Pick the right neural network architecture

- Choose the right neural network architecture for the problem at hand.
- The "backbone" (body) depends on data type:
 - Spatially related data (e.g. images) - Convolutional Neural Networks (Conv-nets).
 - Time series data (e.g. natural language, waveforms, signals) - Recurrent Neural Networks, LSTMs, Transformer models.
 - Tabular, categorical, numerical data – usually multiple dense (fully connected) layers will do.

Pick the right neural network architecture

- The "head" (output) and loss function depends on model objective:
 - Classification – probably Cross Entropy Loss.
 - Image segmentation – a U-net backbone with Cross Entropy Loss.
 - Object detection – bounding box predictions.
- Other popular branches of Deep Learning:
 - Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) - learning and representing distributions - "creative AI".
 - Reinforcement Learning – self-learning in a simulated (for now) environment.
 - Unsupervised, semi-supervised, or self-supervised learning – training models with limited labels.

Pick the right computing hardware

- A laptop or desktop PC (CPU only) is sufficient for experimenting with toy models.
- For serious compute, you need to look at GPUs (or TPUs).
- Option 1: Get a GPU for your desktop PC. Convenient but limited performance.
- Option 2: Use free cloud compute (e.g. Google Colab). Free! But limited runtime and performance.
- Option 3: Buy your own mini-supercomputer, e.g. NVIDIA DGX A100 – 5 Teraflops at USD200K.
- Option 4: Rent compute time on cloud services such as Google Cloud Platform, AWS, Azure. Costs can add up.
- Option 5: Check with your local institution for free or membership based access to HPC.